

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_a_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:24:41 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	40.71	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.6212	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x...filtered (λ s 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_natural_a_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:24:41 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	12.32	μm	
Min:	-6.849	μm	
Max:	5.476	μm	
Size:	198390	digits	
Spacing:	0.06212	nm	
NM-points ratio:	11.51 % (1035886 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_na...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 10:24:41 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	12.32	μm	
Size:	198390	digits	
Spacing:	0.06212	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.584	μm	
Ssk	-0.6095		
Sku	4.876		
Sp	5.466	μm	
Sv	6.859	μm	
Sz	12.32	μm	
Sa	1.125	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.4839	%	
Smc	1.693	μm	
Sxp	3.991	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	19.52	μm	
Str	0.4801		
Std	42.25	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.3827		
Sdr	6.003	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.08953	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	1.783	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.08953	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	1.130	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	1.496	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2868	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	7.217	µm
Mean depth of furrows	1.569	µm
Mean density of furrows	3750	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	89.98	°
Second direction	45.01	°
Third direction	180.0	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	73.97	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

